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Unidirectional propagation of zero-momentum magnons ^F

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ABSTRACT

We report on experimental observation of unidirectional propagation of zero-momentum magnons in synthetic antiferromagnet consisting of strained CoFeB/Ru/CoFeB trilayer. Inherent non-reciprocity of spin waves in synthetic antiferromagnets with uniaxial anisotropy results in smooth and monotonous dispersion relation around Gamma point, where the direction of the phase velocity is reversed, while the group velocity direction is conserved. The experimental observation of this phenomenon by intensity-, phase-, and time-resolved Brillouin light scattering microscopy is corroborated by analytical models and micromagnetic simulations.

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Synthetic antiferromagnets (SAFs) recently attracted a lot of attention in the magnonics community, as they can provide additional degrees of freedom for spin wave dispersion engineering compared to conventional ferromagnetic systems.^{1–8} One of the most prominent features of dispersion relation in SAFs is non-reciprocity caused by the dipolar field interaction between the layers.^{9–15} Spin wave non-reciprocity and symmetry breaking in material systems are of fundamental interest and can also be exploited in practical magnonic applications, such as diodes or circulators.¹⁶ Non-reciprocal dispersion can be achieved also in ferromagnets, e.g., by exploiting interfacial effects^{17–20} or current induced Doppler shift.^{21,22} However, the non-reciprocity in SAFs is much more pronounced. Another way to create non-reciprocal spin-wave system is to use a grating coupler,^{14,23} but these systems can be tuned only to a specific k -vector and frequency. Nevertheless, the methodology for modeling spin waves in SAFs is not fully developed, and not all consequences of nonreciprocal dispersion relation are explored.

In this paper, we report on the observation of smooth, monotonous, and steep spin wave dispersion in the vicinity of Γ point ($k=0$) in SAFs. This property leads to unidirectional spin wave propagation over a wide range of frequencies. The group velocity points in the same direction at both sides of the Γ point, whereas the phase velocity

is reversed upon the Γ point crossing [see Fig. 1(a)], resulting in a situation where we can observe unidirectional energy flow with two opposing phase velocities (wavevectors). The smooth, monotonous, and steep dispersion causes that even zero-momentum spin waves (with $k=0$) propagate with nonzero group velocity. This phenomenon exhibits itself as a change of the sign of phase evolution for the same direction of the spin wave propagation and is directly observed by phase-resolved Brillouin light scattering (BLS) microscopy.²⁴

To study this behavior, we prepared a sample consisting of a multilayer stack of two 15 nm thick CoFeB layers separated by a 0.6 nm thick Ru spacer layer, which were grown by magnetron-sputtering on Si(100) substrate covered by the 285 nm thick thermal SiO₂ layer [Fig. 1(b)]. On top of the SAF layer, we patterned a 500 nm wide microwave antenna for spin wave excitation using electron beam lithography and the liftoff process. The antenna consists of a stack of Ti 5 nm/SiO₂ 10 nm/Ti 5 nm/Au 50 nm thin films deposited by e-beam evaporation. The SAF layer was imaged by scanning transmission electron microscopy with a high-angle annular dark-field detector (STEM-HAADF) showing individual layers with Z-contrast, and its chemical composition was investigated by energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (STEM-EDX), see Fig. 1(c). The STEM-HAADF image shows the quality of the interfaces. Note that the quality of the interface

FIG. 1. Experimental geometry. (a) Schematics of the experiment and unidirectional excitation of spin waves with positive and negative wavevectors. Due to the linear dispersion, the group velocity direction is not changed upon the reversal of wavevector direction. (b) Schematics of the studied system. The two CoFeB layers are coupled antiferromagnetically through RKKY (Ruderman–Kittel–Kasuya–Yosida) interaction. (c) STEM image of the lamella prepared under the antenna layer (right panel) and atomic fraction of individual elements obtained by EDX analysis.

of the bottom of the first layer and the top of the second layer is different. This introduces a slight asymmetry into our SAF system, even when the thickness of both layers is the same [$t_{\text{CoFeB}} = (15 \pm 1)$ nm as revealed by the EDX chemical composition profile].

In-plane (IP) and out-of-plane (OOP) hysteresis loops of the sample were acquired by vibrating sample magnetometry (VSM), see Fig. 2(a) and Fig. S2. To obtain static magnetic parameters of the SAF layer, we model the hysteresis loop using minimization of the energy

TABLE I. Fitted and fixed material parameters. t_{CoFeB} is the thickness of the individual CoFeB layers, t_{Ru} is the thickness of the Ru spacer, M_s is the saturation magnetization, J_{bl} (J_{bq}) is the bilinear (biquadratic) interlayer coupling, H_u is the uniaxial anisotropy field, γ is the gyromagnetic ratio, A_{ex} is the exchange constant, and α is the dimensionless damping constant.

Parameter	t_{CoFeB} (nm)	t_{Ru} (nm)	M_s (kA/m)	J_{bl} (mJ/m ²)	J_{bq} (mJ/m ²)	H_u (kA/m)	$\gamma/(2\pi)$ (GHz/T)	A_{ex} (pJ/m)	α
Value	$15 \pm 1^{\text{a}}$	$0.6 \pm 0.2^{\text{a}}$	$1299 \pm 14^{\text{b}}$	$-0.67 \pm 0.02^{\text{b}}$	$-0.28 \pm 0.02^{\text{b}}$	$1.5 \pm 0.2^{\text{c}}$	30^{d}	15^{d}	0.004^{d}

^aMeasured from TEM images.

^bObtained from the simultaneous fit of OOP and IP hysteresis loops.

^cEstimated from the offset of the out-of-plane polarized (acoustic) mode synthetic antiferromagnetic resonance.

^dThese parameters were fixed.¹⁹

FIG. 2. Static characterization of SAF sample. (a) In-plane VSM hysteresis curve, analytic modeling based on energy minimalization, and MuMax3 simulation results. (b) Hysteresis loops measured by wide-field Kerr microscope. The external field was applied perpendicular to uniaxial anisotropy axis. The black (red) curve shows magnetization perpendicular (parallel) to the external field. (c) Positions of the out-of-plane polarized (acoustic) mode measured with the external field parallel and perpendicular to the uniaxial anisotropy axis (black and red squares). The experimental data are compared with the analytical model (red and black solid lines) calculated using the parameters obtained from the fitting of the static hysteresis loops, see panel (a) and Table I.

of two macrospins in a similar manner as it is done in the Stoner–Wohlfarth model.^{25,26} The total energy reads as^{27,28}

$$E = E_{\text{dip}} + E_{\text{Zeeman}} + E_{\text{ex}} + E_{\text{anis}} + E_j + E_{\text{inter}}, \quad (1)$$

where E_{dip} is the dipolar energy, E_{Zeeman} is the energy caused by the external field, E_{ex} is the intralayer exchange, E_{anis} is the energy of uniaxial anisotropy, E_{inter} is the dipolar energy between the two layers, and interlayer exchange $E_j = J_{\text{bl}}(1 - m_1 \cdot m_2) + J_{\text{bq}}[1 - (m_1 \cdot m_2)]^2$, where J_{bl} and J_{bq} are bilinear and biquadratic exchange constants, respectively.^{29,30} Using this model, we obtained saturation

magnetization (M_s) and interlayer coupling constants from the simultaneous fitting of the experimental IP and OOP hysteresis loops. The thickness of the layers was estimated from TEM measurements, and anisotropy was estimated from offset of out-of-plane polarized (acoustic) mode resonance. The fitting results are summarized in Table I. The observed uniaxial anisotropy arises probably from the Ta seed layer roughness.^{31,32}

We also implemented bilinear and biquadratic coupling into MuMax3 code³³ using custom fields. For this, we have to derive the effective field caused by the coupling and switch off the standard exchange interaction between the layers. The discretized effective coupling field B_j then reads as

$$B_j = \frac{\partial E_j}{\partial \mathbf{M}} = \frac{\sum_i \mathbf{m}_i - \mathbf{m}}{c_z M_s} \left(J_{bl} + 2J_{bq} \sum_i \mathbf{m}_i \cdot \mathbf{m} \right), \quad (2)$$

where c_z is the cell size in the OOP direction and i is the layer index. The results [see Fig. 2(a), circles] are in perfect agreement with the experiment and results from Eq. (1), which proves that the implementation of the coupling constants in MuMax3 is valid, and the code can also be used for simulations of dispersion relations.

To get further insight into the sample static behavior, we performed wide-field Kerr microscopy with the external magnetic field applied at different angles to the easy axis of the SAF. The magnetization components perpendicular and parallel to the applied field direction are shown in Fig. S3, together with corresponding loops obtained from the energy minimalization. When the external magnetic field is applied perpendicularly to the easy axis, it is possible to stabilize the single domain state, with the Néel vector aligned with the easy axis, see Fig. 2(b). This property of the studied system is essential for later BLS experiments, which are performed in zero external magnetic field.

Angle-resolved Kerr microscopy experiments revealed that the switching is deterministic and depends on the magnetic field sweep direction (see the [supplementary material](#), Fig. S4). This deterministic switching is unexpected in perfectly symmetric SAFs. Here, it is probably caused by slightly different magnetic properties of the individual layers or interfaces,³⁴ thus slightly different total energies for the two opposite directions of magnetization. It could be also caused by different layer thicknesses, but our STEM data [Fig. 1(c)] do not show any difference above the measurement uncertainty of ± 1 nm. However, as mentioned earlier, there is a difference in the quality of the interfaces between the top and bottom layers that can cause this deterministic behavior.

Out-of-plane polarized (acoustic) mode of SAF was measured by using vector network analyzer (VNA) in flip chip configuration³⁵ in two geometries: with the external magnetic field perpendicular and parallel to the easy axis of the SAF, see the [supplementary material](#), Fig. S5. The positions of out-of-plane polarized (acoustic) mode, determined by fitting the Lorentz function for each applied external magnetic field, are shown in Fig. 2(c). The experimental data agree well with the analytic model of out-of-plane polarized (acoustic) mode [shown in Fig. 2(c) as black and red lines] developed by Gallardo *et al.*^{27,28} This model is based on solving the following eigenproblem (assuming $k = 0$):

$$\hat{A} \mathbf{m} = i \left(\frac{\omega}{\mu_0 \gamma} \mathbf{m} \right), \quad (3)$$

where \hat{A} is a system matrix, ω is a spin-wave frequency, γ is a gyromagnetic ratio, and \mathbf{m} is a dynamic normalized magnetization vector in both layers. The system matrix depends on the sample geometry (CoFeB and Ru thicknesses), magnetization orientation of the individual CoFeB layers {obtained by energy minimization [see Eq. (1)]}, and the magnetic properties (saturation magnetization M_s , exchange constant A_{ex} , uniaxial anisotropy field H_u , and interlayer exchange coupling J_{bl} and J_{bq}). To calculate results shown in Figs. 2(c), 3(a), and 4(c), we used parameters from Table I.

FIG. 3. Unidirectional excitation of the spin waves in SAF. (a) Dispersion relation obtained by the analytic model and MuMax3 simulation. The red curve shows the excitation efficiency of the used antenna. (b) BLS intensity measured approximately $1.5 \mu\text{m}$ away from the antenna in the positive (red symbols) and the negative (black symbols) z-direction. (c) Two-dimensional mapping of the spin-wave intensity at the frequency of 2.5 GHz. Arrows depict directions of uniaxial anisotropy and magnetizations. (d) Extracted spin-wave phase from five BLS measurements at 2.5 GHz.

To obtain SAF dispersion, we can use the same analytic model (Eq. 3), which can be extended for $k \in [-20 \text{ rad}/\mu\text{m}, 20 \text{ rad}/\mu\text{m}]$ [gray line in Fig. 3(a)]. To further confirm the results of the analytic model, we performed micromagnetic simulations in MuMax3 [see colormap in Fig. 3(a)]. The simulation cell size was set to $(10 \times 10) \text{ nm}^2$ in the IP direction and 15 nm in the OOP direction, i.e., we neglected the Ru spacer and assumed only one cell per one CoFeB layer. The simulation size was $2048 \times 2048 \times 2$ cells. More details on the micromagnetic simulations and subsequent analysis can be found in the supplementary note 1 and in Ref. 36.

Before BLS experiments, we stabilized the single-domain magnetization state in wide-field Kerr microscope. The Néel vector pointed parallel to the strip line antenna (connected to RF generator), which was used to excite spin waves in the SAF layer. As the first BLS experiment, we swept the excitation frequency and compared the BLS spectra acquired at a distance of $1.5 \mu\text{m}$ from the antenna on both sides, see Fig. 3(b). Higher excitation efficiency on the positive side of the antenna is clearly visible. On the negative side, the spin wave signal above 2 GHz is completely suppressed. In this region, the antenna cannot efficiently excite spin waves due to the low excitation efficiency of the antenna for spin waves with a wavelength shorter than the width of the antenna, see Fig. 3(a), red line. The excitation efficiency was calculated using fast Fourier transform of the in-plane component of the field calculated by the FEMM (finite element method magnetics) solver.³⁷ The signal below 2 GHz visible on the negative side of the antenna originates from the dispersion region with negative group velocity ($k < -5 \text{ rad}/\mu\text{m}$). Note that this signal can be entirely suppressed by modifying the excitation efficiency, i.e., by using a slightly wider antenna, thus, the spin wave emission can be completely unidirectional, see supplementary note 2.

To further investigate this non-reciprocal behavior, we performed a 2-dimensional mapping of BLS signal at the frequency of 2.5 GHz, as

shown in Fig. 3(c). At this frequency, we can observe unidirectional excitation of uniform spin waves. We have performed full phase-resolved mapping of spin waves with the use of five different measurements.³⁸ The results [Fig. 3(d)] show clear spatially uniform evolution of the phase in the direction perpendicular to the antenna in the positive z -direction. On the other side of the antenna, no phase evolution was observed.

As the next experiment, we performed two full phase-resolved linescans in the direction perpendicular to the antenna at the frequencies of 1.8 and 2.6 GHz and extracted the intensity and phase of spin waves [Figs. 4(a) and 4(b)]. For 1.8 GHz, we can observe a negative phase evolution in the positive values of z [upper side of the antenna in Figs. 3(c) and 3(d)]. On the other hand, at the frequency of 2.6 GHz, we can observe a positive phase evolution on the same side of the antenna. The intensity data show prominent non-reciprocity, where exponential decay is visible only toward the positive direction [the decay constants for negative direction are $0.65 \pm 0.04 \mu\text{m}$ (1.8 GHz) and $0.49 \pm 0.03 \mu\text{m}$ (2.6 GHz), and for positive direction $0.84 \pm 0.06 \mu\text{m}$ (1.8 GHz) and $1.9 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$ (2.6 GHz)]. By repeating this experiment at different frequencies, we obtained full dispersion relation (gray squares) and frequency-dependent phase velocity (red squares), see Fig. 4(c). We also performed time-resolved BLS experiments and extracted group velocities [see red circles in Fig. 4(c) and Fig. S6]. The experimental data agree well with our analytical model [see solid and dashed lines in Fig. 4(c)].

Spin waves at the Γ point ($k = 0$) are shifted up by approximately 1.9 GHz, which agrees well with the data in Fig. 2(c), and is caused by the uniaxial anisotropy. The anisotropy and the dipolar interaction induce the monotonous and smooth dispersion through the Γ point and lead to unidirectional group velocity [see dashed line in Fig. 4(c)]. The group velocity is conserved despite the change of the

FIG. 4. Phase velocity reversal upon Γ point crossing. (a) and (b) Spin-wave intensity (blue squares) and spin-wave phase (black squares) at 1.8 (a) and 2.6 GHz (b). The red and blue lines are fits of the linear evolution of phase and exponential decay of spin waves, respectively. (c) Dispersion relation and phase velocity obtained experimentally (black and red squares) and by analytic modeling (black and red solid lines). Group velocity measured by time-resolved BLS (red circles) and calculated from the analytical model (red dashed line). (d) Simulated space-time map of the zero-momentum spin-wave evolution. The configuration is the same as in Fig. 1(a). Black dashed line shows the group velocity. The appearance of the spin wave in the left part of the space-time map is caused by periodic boundary conditions used in the simulation.

wavenumber (phase velocity) from positive to negative. This allows the direction of energy flow to remain constant even when the phase velocity changes sign due to changes in the medium or excitation frequency. In addition, the wave packets consisting of the waves with opposite wavenumbers can be constructed and propagated in the same direction.

This property leads to interesting phenomena, where the wave with zero momentum ($k = 0$) can still propagate in space. To demonstrate this, we performed micromagnetic simulation where the dynamics was excited by OOP sinc pulse centered at $z = 0 \mu\text{m}$. The evolution of the whole excited spin wave packet in space and time is shown in Fig. S7. If we filter only wavevectors with $k \rightarrow 0$, we can clearly see the propagation of this “wave” toward the positive value of z [see Fig. 4(d)]. The phase velocity $v_p \rightarrow \infty$, while the group velocity $v_g = 2.3 \mu\text{m/ns}$ is given by the dispersion relation [see Fig. 4(c)], which is also in agreement with simple formula given in Ref. 13 ($v_g = 2.31 \pm 0.03 \mu\text{m/ns}$). The orientation of the unidirectional propagation can be reversed by switching the SAF magnetization (see the [supplementary material](#), Fig. S8).

In conclusion, we observed unidirectional propagation of zero-momentum magnons in synthetic antiferromagnet. Inherent non-reciprocity of spin waves in synthetic antiferromagnets with uniaxial anisotropy shapes the dispersion relation into a smooth and monotonous function in the vicinity of the Γ point. This situation leads to unidirectional propagation of spin waves with negative, zero, and positive wavenumbers. This phenomenon was observed by intensity-, phase-, and time-resolved BLS microscopy and further corroborated by micromagnetic simulations and analytical modeling. Such unusual dispersion relation only occurs for planetary waves (e.g., Yanai waves), where the control of experimental condition is impossible.³⁹ Therefore, our system offers many possibilities for further investigations of related phenomena, e.g., propagation of wavepackets with bidirectional phase velocities or spin wave accumulation on domain boundaries. In practical applications, such unidirectional system can pave the way toward designing new types of non-reciprocal elements for signal processing and unconventional spin-wave computing.

See the [supplementary material](#) for more details on the micromagnetic simulations, additional experimental data confirming the complete suppression of spin-wave excitation in one direction using a wider antenna, and six additional figures supporting the claims made in the main text.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Ondřej Wojewoda: Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (equal); Investigation (lead); Software (equal); Visualization (equal); Writing – original draft (lead). **Jakub Holobrádek:** Investigation (supporting); Resources (lead); Writing – review & editing (supporting). **Dominik Pavelka:** Investigation (supporting); Writing – review & editing (supporting). **Ekaterina Pribytova:** Resources (supporting). **Jakub Krčma:** Investigation (supporting). **Jan Klíma:** Resources (supporting); Software (supporting); Writing – review & editing (supporting). **Jaganandha Panda:** Resources (equal). **Jan Michalička:** Investigation (supporting); Writing – review & editing (supporting). **Tomáš Lednický:** Resources (supporting); Writing – review & editing (supporting). **Andrii V. Chumak:** Conceptualization (supporting); Writing – review & editing (supporting). **Michal Urbánek:** Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (equal); Funding acquisition (lead); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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